

The physical constants and antimicrobial data of the compounds thus prepared are given in Table 2.

Antimicrobial screening :

The purified products were screened for antimicrobial activity by cup plate method¹ using *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. The testing was carried out in ethanol solution at a concentration 10 mg/ml. The zone of inhibition of the test solution (0.5 mg) was recorded. Most of the anils are active against gram positive bacteria only while 4-thiazolidinones, containing 5-H/methyl were active against both gram positive and gram negative.

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Biological Activity of 2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-p-azobenzene Sulphonamido Thiazoles

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AZO dyes are well known for their antiseptic activity^{1,2} and some are useful as chemotherapeutic agents³. A number of thiazole compounds have been tested for antibacterial⁴, antifungal⁵, antitumor⁶ and anthelmintic activity⁷. Sulphonamides are known antibacterial agents. Since 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole has been reported to possess antifungal activity⁸ and some 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-arylazothiazoles are reported to possess possible anticancer activity⁹,

coupling of diazotized sulphonamide with 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole was expected to yield compounds with increased antibacterial, antifungal and anticancer activity. With this in view, various sulphonamides were prepared to yield compounds (I) and to study their biological activities.

The compound (I) described here have been synthesized by reacting the diazotized sulphonamides with 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole by the established method⁹. The structure of these compounds have been established on the basis of elemental analysis and ir spectral studies and homogeneity by tlc technique.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded by KBr disc method on Perkin-Elmer 377 IR spectrophotometer and uv spectra on Beckman DU₂ spectrophotometer. TLC was done using silica gel G as adsorbent and chloroform-methanol (85 : 15) as solvent.

Preparation of 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-p-azobenzene sulphonamido thiazole (1; R=H): The sulphonamide (0.01 mole) was dissolved in 3 equivalent of hydrochloric acid and the solution was cooled to 0-5°. A cold solution of sodium nitrite (0.02 mole) was added dropwise with stirring. After completion of the reaction any excess of nitrous acid was destroyed by careful addition of urea. 2-Amino-4-phenyl thiazole (0.01 mole) was dissolved in alcohol (25 ml) and sodium acetate (0.01 mole) was added. The solution was cooled to 0-5°. To this, the solution of diazonium salt of sulphonamide was added with stirring. A bright coloured product was obtained. It was crystallised from alcohol-DMF mixture. All the compounds gave characteristic peaks $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ between 1648-1520 (aromatic nuclei, C=N, C=C and N=N) and 1355-1335, 1165-1150 cm^{-1} (SO_2NH) and show $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ at 270 nm. (Compound 1, m.p. 246-247°; Found: N, 19.32. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_5\text{O}_2\text{S}_2$; N, 19.49%).

The analysis data of the compounds prepared are given in Table 1.

Preliminary antimicrobial and antifungal activity was studied by disc diffusion plate method. 1 : 500 and 1 : 1000 solutions of the test compounds were made in Tween 80-water (20 : 80). A control was run simultaneously. Moderate to feeble antibacterial activity was recorded against *Proteus vulgaris*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus lutea*. No antifungal activity was shown by the compounds when tested against *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizopus nigrican* and *Helminthosporium aptilinae*

while noticeable activity was recorded against *Alternaria brassicae*.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF 2-AMINO-4-PHENYL-5-P-AZOBENZENE SULPHOANAMIDO THIAZOLES

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	R _f
1.	Hydrogen	246-247	85	0.88
2.	Guanidinyl	238-240	90	0.76
3.	Acetyl	202-208	85	0.90
4.	2-(1-Phenyl pyrazolyl)	199-201	80	0.87
5.	3-(5-Methyl isoxazolyl)	201-208	80	0.94
6.	2-Thiazolyl	225-227	90	0.88
7.	2-(5-Methyl 1,3,4-thiadiazolyl)	230-282	85	0.74
8.	4-(2,6-Dimethyl pyrimidyl)	233-235	80	0.94
9.	2-(Pyrimidyl)	228-235	95	0.78
10.	2-(4,6-Dimethyl pyrimidyl)	209-211	80	0.72

All compounds gave consistent nitrogen analysis.

Anticancer activity test was done at Tata Cancer Research Institute, Bombay against mouse tumour system P 388 but all the compounds were found inactive.

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Constituents of *Rhus punjabensis*

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FAMILY Anacardiaceae which consists of 73 genera and about 600 species is rich for its biflavonoidic constituents. The genus *Rhus*, one of the largest genera of the family, is chiefly distributed in the warm temperature region of both hemispheres extending into the tropical and cold temperature region. An attempt has been made to study the

complex mixture of biflavonoids in the leave extracts of *Rhus punjabensis* (procured from Gopeshwar Hills, Chamoli Distt., India).

The phenolic extractives after preliminary purification and tlc examination on silica gel using benzene-pyridine-acetic acid (36:9:5)¹ developing solvent showed two bands, labelled as RPI and RPII. They were separated by preparative thin layer chromatography.

Although RPI was chromatographically homogeneous, on methylation and tlc examination it was found to be a mixture of three methyl ethers, one major and two minor ones. The major methyl ether labelled as RPIMII was separated by preparative tlc, and characterized as agathisflavone hexamethyl ether, m.p. 162-64°, by spectral analysis and comparison with authentic sample^{2,3}. The two minor methyl ethers, obtained by methylation of RPI, were identified as amentoflavone and robustaflavone hexamethyl ethers by comparison with authentic samples (R_f values, characteristic fluorescence in uv light and co-tilc)^{4,5}.

RPII was identified as hinokiflavone, i.e. 1-5, 11-5, 1-7, 11-7, 11-4' pentahydroxy (1-4'-O-11-8) flavone by its spectral properties as well as those of its methyl ether, m.p. 260-64° and acetate, m.p. 237-40°.

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Synthesis and Ion-Exchange Properties of Thermally Stable Stannic Silico Selenite: Separation of Cu²⁺ from Zn²⁺ and Mn²⁺

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SYNTHETIC inorganic ion-exchangers are found to be thermally more stable than their organic counterparts but the search for materials with still greater thermal stability continues. The thermal stability of silica (SiO₂.xH₂O), a naturally occurring weak inorganic ion-exchanger, is very high. Literature reveals that silica has been used in synthesising

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